

LANGUAGE TEACHING AND MEDIA LITERACY

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Annotation: in this article highlights of using innovative methods in the teaching Language. The purpose of this article is to present a proposal for using media resources in the classroom. The underlying reason is to raise awareness of the potential that the mass media product offers in teaching a foreign language and to point out that we have more material within easy reach than we believe. First, I will discuss the role of mass media in language development and language teaching in particular. Second, I will put forward a proposal for using mass media products which involves discussing the role of mother tongue and of genre theory with regard to dealing with diversity or different levels in the classroom. Third, I will give some examples of the types of exercises that may be useful and easy to design for using mass media resources in teaching English, or any other foreign language.

Key words: Effectiveness of Technology in Language Education, Limitations of Research Studies, Literature Review, Media.

The Mass Media As teachers of foreign languages, we are now teaching a generation that is privileged in their knowledge of mass media. As argued by Connell et al. (1996:10), "no generation has a bigger media history because no previous generation has had access to so many different kinds of media and such a range of media products". Before radio and television, the students' only access to knowledge was the school. Nowadays, the media precede us. When students come to school, they have already learned a great deal from TV, radio, internet, etc., a fact that we should not ignore but take advantage of. There is practically no way of avoiding the mass media. They are part of our life. Thus, if we teach students how to analyse mass media products we are helping the student to develop a whole range of individual, practical, social, cultural and intellectual skills which they will need in the future. We ought to start taking TV, computer games, internet, etc. seriously and use them not only as teaching material but as an efficient way to motivate the students. We should make them understand how these mass media work, that is, our students should be media literate.

Among the mass media, it is clear that television has the greatest significant and continued impact on our present culture. Watching television is the third activity after work and sleep which occupies most of our time; more than 56%

of the Spanish population admits that TV is their only pastime (FerrÈs 1998). As argued by Gronbeck (1979:3) with regard to television: "it is specially important because of television's pervasiveness and potential power, that students of all ages be taught a critical attitude and method for exercising that attitude." Along the same lines, FerrÈs (1998:15) argues "si educar exige preparar a los ciudadanos para integrarse de una manera reflexiva y crÌtica en la sociedad, ¿cÙmo se integrar·n unos ciudadanos que no estÈn preparados para realizar de una manera crÌtica aquella actividad a la que m·s horas dedican?" My question is addressed to teachers of foreign languages. That is, if we admit that the mass media have a crucial role in language development, as they do in any societal change, should we not as teachers of English as a foreign language be teaching our students about the language of the mass media? Although it may seem sometimes irrelevant to do exercises based on vocabulary, grammatical structures, pragmatic failure, etc (cf. Gregori, Pennock and Bou 1998), based on certain mass media products, it is not. These exercises help to raise awareness about language features and, in particular, about generic conventions, a first step for developing a critical attitude. As Christie (1985:22) argues: "learning the genres of one's culture is both part of entering into it with understanding, and part of developing the necessary ability to change it." Thus, if students learn about different genres used in the mass media, they will be conscious about what they want to keep and what they want to change in them.

The study of genres has long figured in both academic and media discourse (cf. Altman 1998, Bakhtin 1979, Bhatia 1993, Ventola 1987, Swales 1990, Martin 1985, McCarthy 1998). Hymes (1967:25) includes genre as one of his components of speech and argues that "the notion of genre implies the possibility of identifying formal characteristics traditionally recognised" (1972:65). Genre is, paradoxically, a difficult concept to define but an easy one to understand. The existence of genres is openly admitted in both linguistics and media studies. Borrowing Halliday's words, I believe that "there is a generic structure in all discourse, including the most spontaneous conversation" (Halliday 1978:134) and that, as argued by McCarthy (1998), one has to analyse and go deeply into examples of the same genre to understand each structure. Although a genre is ultimately an abstract conception rather than something that exists empirically in the world (cf. Feuer 1992:144), genre is also, paradoxically, a concept that students can easily grasp, understand and most important, identify. If you ask a student if *Compañeros* and *El Informal* belong to the same genre, they would answer, with no qualms about it, that they do not. In

this sense, studies carried out by Jaglom and Gardner (1981) and Buckingham (1993; quoted in Chandler 1997) have brought about considerable evidence of children using notions of genre, both explicitly and implicitly. As argued by Chandler (1997) children showed an awareness that the programmes could be categorised in several ways. Genre was one of the principles which all of the groups (barring one of the youngest) used in completing the task. Furthermore, the children's repertoire of genre labels increased with age. Buckingham (1993:154) argues that "as their repertoire of terms expands, this enables them to identify finer distinctions between programmes, and to compare them in a greater variety of ways". Hence, a generic approach to media can be very useful in order to classify, organise and use media resources in the classroom. The problem with a generic approach to media products, in particular with regard to television, is that genres are in a constant state of flux and redefinition (cf. Feuer 1992). Intertextuality and hybridness are two key characteristics of television programmes. Hence, White (1985) states, the difficulty to describe and differentiate television programmes according to generic categories (cf. Altman 1984). It is not difficult to assess what types of mass media products the teacher will come across. We may find examples that can be easily assigned to a particular genre; or, on the contrary, we may find examples that deviate from well-established generic conventions. Concerning our choice of programmes to be used in the classroom, we can choose either or alternate between the two—depending on the purpose of each exercise. Whatever our choice, the fact is that different categories such as soap operas, crime dramas, game shows, etc., may be distinguished by their programming slots and an array of shared conventions, which most of us are, in general terms, familiar with. Two questions arise here: 1. How does the teacher get hold of the material? 2. How does s/he design exercises based on that material? The first question is inevitably related to the fact that the production of the mass media is massive and that it is impossible to keep up with everything. So, how is the teacher expected to select the material? How long is it going to take him/her to find that material? How useful is that material going to be? Apart from the material that we can easily buy (cassettes, videos, etc.) we can also devise our own material from television, radio and newspapers data. My first suggestion would be to choose programmes, articles, etc. that are of interest for the students. In doing so, however, one subsequent problem arises: in the case of television programmes, for example, they may be interested in a nationally produced series which is not available in English. Thus, the ensuing question, should we use material which is in the learner's native

language? I will answer this question in section 4. The second question relates to a problem that all teachers face: the design of exercises is time-consuming, specially if it has to do with audio-visual material. Thus, if we have a set of exercises that serves as a basis, and that can be adapted to any mass media product, the task may be immensely simplified for the teacher

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